

WASTE REIMAGINED.

ENERGY REBORN.

At CARMA-H2, we are turning local organic waste into clean hydrogen, offering communities a simple and sustainable way to drive the green transition.

CARMA-H2 introduces a **smarter way to produce hydrogen from organic waste**: the protonic membrane reformer (bioPMR).

Traditional systems like steam methane reforming (SMR) involve high temperatures and multiple complex steps, while bioPMR streamlines everything into a single, efficient process. The result is **clean hydrogen** and **high-purity, food-grade quality CO₂**, made possible by an integrated CO₂ liquefaction system.

Advantages of bioPMR

SCALABILITY → Compact and modular, ideal for decentralised production.

CO₂ MANAGEMENT → Captures CO₂ directly, no extra systems needed.

ENERGY USE → More efficient with microthermal heat recovery and electrochemical separation.

HYDROGEN PURITY → Delivers high-purity H₂ in a single step.

CLEAN HYDROGEN, MADE SIMPLE

SMR (6 STEP PROCESS)

bioPMR (1 STEP PROCESS)

PROJECT GOALS

ECONOMIC GROWTH

CARMA-H2 drives market adoption of bioPMR with integrated CO₂ liquefaction, strengthening a competitive European value chain.

ENVIRONMENTAL IMPACT

By optimising biogas utilisation, CARMA-H2 significantly cuts greenhouse gas emissions and enhances waste valorisation.

SOCIAL BENEFITS

CARMA-H2 fosters job creation across the renewable energy value chain, boosting the hydrogen economy.

SCIENTIFIC INNOVATION

The project pioneers an electrochemical system that operates on raw biogas with minimal pre-treatment.

KEEP IN TOUCH WITH THE PROJECT

DISCOVER MORE:
visit CARMA-H2 website
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PROJECT PILOT

CARMA-H2 demonstrates the bioPMR technology at the Arazuri wastewater treatment plant in **Navarra, Spain** (EDAR Arazuri, 31170).